

SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS OF FORMATION OF PREMARITAL MATURITY IN YOUNG PEOPLE

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Annotation: In this article, we will learn about factors of maturity before marriage, age of marriage, psychological problems before marriage. We analyze the psychological crises of puberty and their period of preparation for marriage, the psychological aspects of forming the all-round maturity of students before marriage. Studying the motives of preparing young people for a family, we will pay special attention to the section "Family psychology" within the framework of the science of psychology.

Key words: marriage, maturity, family psychology, student, crisis, physical maturity, spiritual and moral maturity, psychological maturity, sexual maturity, moral maturity, legal maturity, marriage age, motives for marriage, family relations, family conflicts .

It is known that as long as human society exists, the sacred place called family continues to take root. Family is a sacred place. The greater the role of the family in the formation of society, the more important the society is for the family. Family is a part of society. Society is made up of families. In society, the family has its own tasks, and each family must follow them and protect its own fortress of happiness. We know that there are many nations in the world and the common concept for all of them is family. But every nation and people have their own national customs, values and traditions. National values are especially important in the process of building a family. Building a family relies on factors such as these values, customs, historical traditions, and lifestyle.

The influence of premarital factors is very important for starting a family. Many socio-economic, biological-physiological, spiritual, moral and psychological factors that are the basis for the occurrence of marriage are also important. There are mainly six pre-marriage factors:

1. Maturity for family life.
2. Motives for starting a family.
3. Dating period before marriage.
4. Marriage age.
5. Conditions of marriage.
6. Concepts of family life.

The concept of maturity for marriage is a stage of human development, an indicator with qualitative and quantitative characteristics. If we connect maturity to marriage with age, the sexual maturity of young people will be a separate topic. This is very important for marriage, because the biological and physiological maturity of young people ensures that the family lives together and lives happily for a long time. It depends on the age limit for marriage. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the age of marriage is strictly set at 18 years old, only in some exceptional cases (the elderly grandmother of the young people who are getting married, the wishes of their grandfathers, the occurrence of some adverse circumstances, the fact that one of the close relatives is seriously ill, etc.) it is established that it is allowed from the age of 17. This takes into account their sexual maturity and legal maturity.

Citizenship, legal maturity - it determines the freedom of a person to have all legal rights, to start a family, to have children.

Vocational maturity is the ability of young people who are about to start a family to have excellent knowledge and the ability to work in their chosen profession after graduating from a certain educational institution.

Socio-economic maturity is the ability of a family member to independently support his family financially.

Ethical maturity is learning about the norms of morality, moral formation, thinking about good behavior, reaching the level of being able to observe and teach the norms of behavior in society.

Psychological maturity is the ability to understand family conditions, to think independently psychologically, to have one's own views about the family and to integrate them into their psychology, to understand the feelings and psychological states of the opposite sex.

Today, the science of family psychology has developed a classification of marriage motives of young people of marriageable age. According to him, the motives of marriage are the reason, the motive, which is the basis for marriage.

The first type is to build a family because of love. These young people fall in love before starting a family.

The second type is to start a family due to material or other interests. The purpose of these young people to start a family is to start a family for the sake of financial resources, wealth, and social interest.

The third type is building a family according to a stereotype. Representatives of this type look at stereotypes when building a family. That is, they think like "this happens to everyone, I did it because I needed to do it, I built a family because I

needed to build a family..." According to statistics, today the most stable and long-term family is those who built a family according to this stereotype. Since the representatives of this family look at life's difficulties as "this happens to everyone", there are very few disagreements in such families, and the number of divorces is also small.

Building a family is a very complicated process. Because every young person who intends to start a family first of all wants a perfect person who fully matches his desires and wishes. He wants the person with whom he will walk the path of his life to be suitable for him, to be perfect in all respects and, most importantly, to conform to moral norms. This is natural. If the main purpose of starting a family is to have children, it may depend on several other factors. The most important thing in a family is MUTUAL RESPECT. The subject of "Adolescent and Pedagogical Psychology" and its "Family Psychology" department will help students to prepare for life, acquire knowledge about pre-marital maturity and be able to apply this knowledge. Of course, we can get to know and study the social and psychological mechanisms of pre-marriage maturity formation in the above literature.

Discussion: First of all, the role of parents, then neighborhood, educational institutions, work activities, and most importantly, society, is incomparable in the formation of premarital maturity. That is why today psychological issues taught in the field of biology in general secondary education, "Family psychology" branch of science taught to students in higher education and "Family preparation courses" organized in neighborhoods, "Family many works are being carried out by the institutes.

Conclusion: In conclusion, the study of family psychology gives us general information about marriage. Develops information for the formation of pre-marital maturity. It helps prepare young people for marriage. Forms students' knowledge about marriage.

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